

PAYING ATTENTION TO THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL PART IN IMPROVING THE DIDACTIC BASIS OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR EFFECTIVE COOPERATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article pays special attention to the issues of improving the didactic foundations of preparing future teachers for effective cooperative activities within the framework of cooperation competence, which is becoming more and more important today. It was considered necessary to give important recommendations and suggestions mainly in theoretical and practical processes.*

Keywords: *collaborative activity, future teacher, didactic conditions, didactic foundations, research materials.*

Today, in the rapidly developing modern world, the role and importance of education is changing rapidly. In particular, the diversity of its types at the present time, the clearly expressed commodity form causes the transformation of education into consumer goods. It should also be said that in educational institutions, like other types of modern economy, the issue of preparing future teachers for cooperative activities is also relevant.

It is permissible to pay attention to the didactic foundations of the process in preparing future teachers for collaborative activities. The most important thing is that it is more beneficial to thoroughly study the didactic foundations of training future teachers for collaborative work and improve it. It can be said that the preparation of the teacher for samurai cooperative activity is an integral part of the process of professional development.

Scientific research works related to didactics, based on a large number of world-class literatures, including scientific publications on the problem, and about 20 dissertation works on didactic education, more than 50 small-volume scientific works devoted to them, other research problems. The analysis in the context of solving shows that preparing future teachers for collaborative activities is considered a sufficiently developed aspect of domestic and foreign theory and practice of teacher education. Strengthening the readiness of future teachers for effective cooperative activities in the broad framework of the pedagogical society, in which attention to the improvement of the didactic framework is recognized as an urgent problem of improving the qualifications of teachers of various specializations and specialties at all levels of the lifelong education system.

We know that the state of modern education at the same time is characterized by the improvement of the general and professional education system, the search for new methods of organizing the educational process at a qualitatively new level. For this reason, the higher education system is moving away from uniformity and standardization. The leading principle of modern changes is to develop the ability of future teachers to work collaboratively in the context of the diversity of educational institutions and changing educational programs, as well as to ensure their readiness for effective collaborative activities. In this place, it is important not to forget the

didactic basis of training and, most importantly, to improve the didactic basis from the current state[1]. One of the approaches to solving the problem identified as a result of the study of this problem is to determine and justify the ability to improve didactic conditions and pedagogical mechanisms of their creation without changing them in the educational practice of higher educational institutions based on modern requirements. It should also be clarified that the existing system of pedagogical education, in addition, all the necessary theoretical and methodological conditions have been created for the implementation of such an approach in local professional pedagogy. If we pay attention to the changes and reforms in the field of education in recent years, it turns out that a number of scientific research studies have been conducted that study some aspects of the process of training future teachers and forming the necessary professional qualities in them. At the same time, despite the many works devoted to various issues of improving the training of future teachers, this problem cannot be considered completed. Some authors disagree about the possibility, necessity, and sometimes expediency of using certain technologies, forms, methods, techniques, and training manuals for these purposes. In general, the features of training for the practical pedagogical process and, in particular, its manifestation in the educational practice of pedagogic educational institutions, have not been fully taken into account. For this reason, it is an urgent direction of scientific and applied research to continue research on the improvement of the didactic foundations of training future teachers, in particular, their preparation for effective cooperative activities, and the search for approaches to improving the pedagogical component[2].

The practical aspects of improving the didactic foundations of preparing future teachers for effective cooperative activities are an aspect that should be given as much importance as highlighting other problems. It is important to pay special attention to the following in relation to this problem in the theoretical research work on improving the didactic foundations of training future teachers for effective cooperative activities:

- theoretical and methodological analysis of pedagogical literature;
- to study the experience of preparing future teachers for effective collaborative activities;
- in-depth study of the necessary regulatory documents regulating its organization and content in higher educational institutions;
- analysis and synthesis of search results in information search systems; development of a complex research program;
- predicting the results of experimental work.

These serve to clarify the level of development of the problem in pedagogical theory and practice and open doors of great opportunities to determine the ways of its optimal solution.

It is also important to clarify the didactic conditions for improving the didactic foundations of training future teachers for effective cooperative activities. And the use of abstraction, concretization, analogy, systematization, and modeling in the process of substantiating this helps to achieve a high target result. In particular, at the experiential stage, it is recommended to use express tests, questionnaires, interviews, monitoring of students' educational activities, expert evaluation methods, including self-evaluation of students, pedagogical experiential methods, and statistical methods of information processing. At the same time, these methods and technologies, which have maintained their above-mentioned constant activity in scientific research work and have not lost their activity due to the fact that the results are effective, are a didactic condition for improving the didactic foundations of preparing future teachers for effective collaborative activities in the educational processes of higher educational institutions. - plays a role in expanding

the process of creating conditions and the possibility of monitoring their results. The practical significance of this research is that its results are aimed at improving the process of professional and personal development in the preparation of future teachers for effective collaborative activities, didactic conditions and pedagogical mechanisms of their creation by the educational practice of universities. Including, the process of pedagogical training of future specialists is no exception. Research materials — methodological developments for lessons, a bank of test tasks, programs of pedagogical seminars, pedagogical practices, a set of methodological tasks in the system of additional education and professional development, not only for future teachers, but also for those who have already started their work. It can also be used to determine the qualifications of selected specialists.

It was also mentioned above that it is necessary to pay attention to the didactic conditions of improving the didactic foundations of training future teachers for effective cooperative activities. What exactly they stand out in is the following:

- in the integration of pedagogical knowledge into the content of pedagogical sciences;
- in the modeling of pedagogical education according to the principles of the innovative approach;
- in organizing creative cooperation between future teachers in spiritual and educational terms;
- in the organization of creative cooperation of future teachers within the framework of pedagogical sciences.

These conditions are interdependent and complex in nature, in which the system-forming function is implemented through theoretical modeling of pedagogical preparation and preparation for effective work activities based on the principles of the necessary approach. This allows to take into account the most important features of the problem. And as a part of improving the didactic foundations of training future teachers for effective collaborative activity, consider it as a non-open, dynamic system, and thus combine pedagogical and professional knowledge between teachers of pedagogy and specialized subjects, together it is permissible to provide opportunities for creation.

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